

D1.3. Communication and Dissemination Plan

Project ref. no.	101112346
Project title	PREdictive simulation of finishing operations in steel Additive Manufacturing for optimal SURface integrity
Project duration	1 st July 2023 – 31 st December 2026 (42 months)
Related WP/Task	WP1 / T1.3
Dissemination level	PUBLIC
Deliverable type	REPORT
Document due date	31/12/2023
Actual delivery date	22/12/2023
Deliverable leader	EURECAT
Document status	Submitted

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1. Deliverable Information sheet

Version	Date	Author	Document history/approvals
0.1	07/12/2023	Miriam Vendrell	Draft version circulated to partners
1.0	18/12/2023	Partners	Up-dates included
2.0	22/12/2023	Montserrat Vilaseca	Final version

2. Executive summary

The document presented here outlines the communication and dissemination plan for the SuPreAM project with the objective of informing a wide range of pertinent stakeholders about the project's activities, milestones, results and main outcomes. The responsibility for developing and executing the communication and dissemination plan for SuPreAM lies with Eurecat, as the leader of this task. However, all consortium partners will actively participate in this strategy.

In this deliverable it can be found a comprehensive overview of the main project's target groups, specific key messages tailored for each primary stakeholder group, the planned communication and dissemination activities, as well as the requirements and procedures for reporting, managing and monitoring the different communication and dissemination initiatives.

The communication and dissemination plan encompasses various channels and platforms, including the official public website, activity on social media partners profiles, production of press releases to engage with specialised and general media outlets, development of promotional and advertising materials to be showcased in key conferences, congresses and other events, organisation of workshops and other events to engage with the project's stakeholders, and publication of articles and papers in scientific journals, among other actions.

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6. Terminology and Acronyms

AEPD	Spanish Data Protection Agency
AM	Additive Manufacturing
AMed	Additive Manufactured
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EUT	Eurecat
GA	Google Analytics
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PFEM	Particle Finite Element Method
RFCS	Research Fund for Coal and Steel
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
VCI	Visual Corporate Image
WP	Work Package

7. Introduction to the communication and dissemination plan

The **SuPreAM project**, spanning 42 months and coordinated by Eurecat, is a research project funded by the RFCS programme of the European Commission. The main goal of the project is to **develop and improve the performance and capabilities of a predictive simulation model of finishing operations in steel Additive Manufacturing (AM)**. SuPreAM seeks to optimise the surface integrity of Additive Manufactured and Machined steel components to reduce manufacturing expenditures at the steel industrial sector by minimising the material scrap and reducing the number of re-processing loops during finishing operations.

Eurecat, as the project's coordinator is leading the **WP1 "Project Coordination"**, which includes the **Task 1.3. Dissemination and Exploitation of Results** (managed by Eurecat and involving an active participation from all the consortium partners), which is directly aligned and related to the current deliverable. At this sense, Eurecat is the main responsible for defining the project's Communication and Dissemination Plan as well as executing it in accordance with the defined project timeline.

7.1 Objectives of the SuPreAM communication and dissemination strategy

The main goals of the SuPreAM communication and dissemination plan are:

- Develop novel communication and dissemination activities to raise and improve the global visibility of the project and its results in Europe and beyond.
- Increase awareness regarding the project's solutions, its funding body, and the potential economic, environmental, and social impact on European manufacturing industries and society.
- Effectively exploit and disseminate the project results and actions to a broad audience of relevant stakeholders.
- Disseminate and share the knowledge generated by the project within the scientific and industrial community, providing support for all project activities.
- Train the next generation of researchers and industry professionals.
- Divulge the project results to targeted audiences to facilitate exploitation and ensure successful market uptake.

8. SuPreAM Communication and Dissemination Plan

The document presented here defines the strategy and plan for communication and dissemination activities, including the creation and maintenance of the project public webpage, development of promotional materials, issuance of press releases, publication of scientific papers, organization of workshops and events, and active participation in conferences, fairs and congresses.

Moreover, this deliverable also includes the dissemination objectives, key messages, target audiences and calendar planned for all the activities. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for each communication and dissemination actions will be defined and reported, ensuring the traceability of the activities that are not listed under specific deliverables, milestones or reports.

Communication activities, launched at the inception of the project, will be sustained even after its conclusion. On the contrary, dissemination efforts will begin upon the availability of the first results, concentrating on specific target audiences, and will continue beyond the completion of the project.

Finally, it's crucial to emphasize that, in order to protect the commercial interests of the partners, the release of materials will be selective, with allowances for mandated reports and information provided to the European Commission. In these cases, partners maintain the discretion to decide which aspects of the project's information should be safeguarded by copyright or patents and which can be broadly disseminated. All actions outlined in the plan adhere to the recommendations and guidelines of the European Research Executive Agency for European-funded research and innovation projects¹.

8.1 Target of communication and dissemination

A first analysis of the target audiences for dissemination has been conducted. Four primary stakeholder groups have been identified as the intended audience for communication and dissemination activities. These groups include academia, industry, end-users/customers, and policy makers, encompassing the broader society. For detailed information refer to Figure 1.

¹ https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en

Figure 1: SuPreAM target audiences.

8.2 Channels and key messages

It's important to highlight that the messages within the communication and dissemination plan have been meticulously crafted and customised for each defined stakeholder. These messages will be adjusted to suit various SuPreAM communication and dissemination channels.

Aligned with the primary objectives expected for dissemination and communication, the messages prepared articulate the potential and significance of the research and development undertaken during the project's execution. These messages will be refined into relevant content for diverse audiences, both specialised and non-specialised, ensuring a clear understanding of the actions and results of the SuPreAM project.

The **general messages** that SuPreAM will convey to key stakeholders include:

- SuPreAM, funded by the European Commission under the RFCS programme, will contribute to the development of materials and processes more respectful with the planet.
- SuPreAM results and outputs will respond to current and future challenges in modelling and manufacturing for the development of processes with improved performance, cost-effectiveness and reduced environmental footprint.
- The SuPreAM project contribute to the EC Circular Economy Action Plan and the EU Green Deal by developing circular, safe, and lightweight sustainable materials, which supports the EU emission reduction target of 40% by 2030.

Regarding the channels, SuPreAM project will employ a diverse array of channels and actions for its communication and dissemination activities. Alongside internal dissemination and routine reporting to the RFCS Commission, the following channels will be utilized to reach the specified stakeholder groups:

Figure 2: SuPreAM Communication and Dissemination channels.

9. Management of communication and dissemination

9.1 Responsibilities distribution

The SuPreAM dissemination and communication plan foresees the active involvement and commitment of all project partners for presenting the project and its main results.

As part of Task 1.3 “Dissemination and exploitation of results”, included in the WP1 Project Coordination, together with T1.1 “General project coordination” and T1.2 “Risk management”, a range of activities focused on communication, dissemination and exploitation will be performed. As mentioned previously, Eurecat assumes the lead role and will be the main responsible for coordinating these activities and the dissemination efforts. This encompasses facilitating information sharing within the consortium representatives, overseeing extensive project dissemination, crafting the project’s visual identity and webpage, creating communication and PR materials, and managing content for the project’s social media platforms. In addition, Eurecat will spearhead initiatives to establish synergies with pertinent projects and initiatives, receiving complete support from the entire consortium.

It is expected the contribution of all project partners to ensure the successful execution of communication and dissemination actions, targeting diverse stakeholder groups as outlined in the project’s objectives.

9.2 Requirements

All the communication and dissemination materials generated within the project, including posters, presentations, promotional and advertising documents, publications, etc., distributed either physical or in digital format will prominently feature the EU emblem and the designated funding text. This aligns with EU regulations stipulated in the Grant Agreement.

In accordance with the Grant Agreement “*unless the Agency requests or agrees otherwise or unless it is impossible, any dissemination activity related to the action (including in electronic form, via social media, etc.) and any infrastructure, equipment and major results funded by the grant must:*

- a) *Display the EU emblem*
- b) *Include the following text*

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS): project num. 101112346. This document reflects only SuPreAM consortium view and neither the European Commission or any associated parties are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

When displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence. For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the EU emblem without first obtaining approval from the Agency. This does not, however,

- [Flyer]
 - [Rollup]
 - [Poster]
 - [Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)]
 - [Organisation of a conference]
 - [Organisation of a workshop]
 - [Participation in activities organised jointly with other EU project(s)]
 - [Participation to a conference (POSTER)]
 - [Participation to a conference (TALK)]
 - [Participation to a workshop]
 - [Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop]
 - [Press release]
 - [Social media - LINKEDIN]
 - [Social media - TWITTER]
 - [Trade fair]
 - [Training]
 - [Video/film]
 - [Brokerage event]
 - [Pitch event]
 - [Website]
 - [Scientific publication]
 - [Other]
- **Type of publication:** to be used only for publications, permitting to select from four options (article in journal, conference/workshop proceedings, books/monographies, chapter in books).
 - **Short explanation of the action:** area created to include a description of the action being reported.
 - **Date/month**
 - **Place:** related to events (if applicable)
 - **Type of audience:** with a break down menu to choose from the stakeholders defined in the EU reporting portal:
 - Scientific community (higher education / research)
 - Industry
 - General public
 - Civil society
 - Media
 - Policy makers
 - Investors
 - Customers
 - Other
 - **Number of people of the audience reached.**
 - **Secondary type of audience reached (if applicable).**
 - **Number of people reached in the secondary audience.**
 - **Partner/s and/or list of authors.**
 - **Link/DOI in case of scientific publications.**

9.3.2 KPIs

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been assigned to a number of communication and dissemination activities planned within the project in order to assess their performance and impact by the end of the project. Progress and updates regarding these KPIs will be reported in project review documents and reports, as well as conveyed in following project meetings. The main KPIs are included and described in Table 1.

Table 1: Dissemination and communication-related KPIs.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target M42
Website	Number of website visits	website Analytics (GA tool)	>2,000
	Updates per year		3 updates / year
Social Media	Twitter: Number of tweets in partners' accounts	Twitter Analytics	>30
	YouTube: Number of videos uploaded	YouTube Analytics	>1
	YouTube: Number of video views		>500
Media relations	LinkedIn: Number of posts in partners' accounts	LinkedIn Analytics	>50
	Number of press releases	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>2
	Articles published in generalist EU outlets		>10
Articles published in key specialised magazines	>5		
Events	Number of events participated (targeting industry and academia)	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>6
	Number of workshops organised		>3
	Number of workshop attendees		>30
Publications	Number of scientific publications	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>4 (30% in cooperation with 2 or more partners)
Training activities	Number of courses, summer schools, masters / PhD programs participated	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>2
Clustering activities	Number of clustering activities with related projects and initiatives	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>3
	Audio-visual materials	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	>1
Promotional Materials	Number of roll-ups / poster	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	1
	Number of factsheet	Proof in dissemination reports / project meetings	1

9.3.3 Risks and mitigation measures

The early risks linked to communication and dissemination, along with the anticipated contingency plans are presented to ensure the proper management of adverse situations throughout the project's evolution. The following graph provides a schematic representation of the SuPreAM risk process.

The exposure to a given risk is estimated using the risk matrix as following:

Impact \ Probability	1- Extremely unlikely	2- Likely	3- Extremely likely
1- Not critical	1	2	3
2- Significant	2	4	6
3- Fundamental to continuing operations	3	6	9

Risk score = Impact x Probability

Priority: ■ High ■ Medium ■ Low

Figure 4: Risk management matrix.

The different risks related with the completion of activities outlined in T1.3 and the associated potential mitigation measures have been identified and described in the following table. While no risks related to dissemination and communication actions were initially identified during the project proposal phase, some risks have been identified while preparing this present deliverable.

Table 2: SuPreAM risks and mitigation measures.

Risks	Probability	Impact	Risk score	Mitigation measures
The complexity of SuPreAM work and research poses challenges for audience comprehension.	2	3	4 Medium	<p>Prepare and elaborate all the communication project material (website, posts on Social Media, etc.) using as much as possible plain language.</p> <p>Exemplify the technology developed and/or research done by using practical use cases.</p> <p>Diversify contexts adapted to the specific needs of the audience.</p>
Inadequate and/or low engagement of project partners in the communication and dissemination activities of SuPreAM	2	2	4 Medium	<p>Organise specific communication and dissemination periodic meetings to analyse the causes and find solutions.</p> <p>Involve all the consortium members and monitor regularly the progress of completed actions to find future solutions.</p>
Limited involvement, engagement and participation in dissemination activities	2	2	4 Medium	<p>Define an intensive communication and promotion campaign of each event.</p> <p>Use relevant channels relevant for our audience.</p> <p>Start promoting the event at least 1 month in advance.</p>
Reduced project visibility	1	2	2 Low	<p>Review the initial webpage of the project to create more engagement content.</p> <p>Update regularly the website with new information.</p> <p>Collaboration in joint activities with other related initiatives and/or projects.</p>

				<p>Enhance the creation of audiovisual materials for widespread use on web platforms like YouTube. L</p> <p>Leverage project partners participating in relevant EU projects and initiatives to act as ambassadors for SuPreAM project, amplifying project dissemination and stakeholder engagement efforts.</p>
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9.4 Ethics, gender, and inclusiveness

The SuPreAM project is prioritizing ethical, societal, and inclusive considerations in its decision-making throughout its implementation. With a specific emphasis on gender equality, project partners are dedicated to ensuring that project images reflect principles and values of fairness and equality. In the design and construction of the project webpage, partners have meticulously selected images, avoiding stereotypes in technology and steering clear of historical assumptions related to gender, ethnicity, and religion.

Furthermore, efforts towards gender sensitivity and inclusiveness extend to the development of messages that consider gender perspectives, as well as ensuring gender balance in round tables and speakers' panels. The Eurecat Research Communication Office teams responsible for overseeing project communication and dissemination activities, has undergone training in non-sexist communication and gender-perspective communication.

Communication and dissemination from SuPreAM emphasize truthfulness, accuracy, honesty, and reason as essential elements for communication integrity. Other guiding principles include upholding freedom of expression, embracing a diversity of perspectives, and promoting tolerance. Importantly, expressions of hate and discrimination are actively condemned across all the project's communication channels.

The SuPreAM project is dedicated to transparent communication as a responsibility to the funding organisation and taxpayers (citizens) who finance the research activities done during the project. This commitment remains unwavering, with due consideration for partner confidentiality regarding specific details about the technologies and innovations being developed. The application of ethical and inclusive principles contributes to enhanced credibility, transparency, and honesty, thereby fostering increased support from the funding organisation and greater engagement from citizens.

Within project meetings, WPs leaders, tasks responsible and participants in communication and dissemination actions are encouraged to raise potential ethical issues and values for collective discussion.

10. Communication tools and activities

10.1 Branding and templates

10.1.1 Project Visual Corporate Image materials

As part of the communication activities of the project, managed by Eurecat, it has been designed and developed the official Visual Corporate Image (VCI) for SuPreAM. The implementation of the VCI has the objective to ensure a harmonised presentation of all communication materials throughout the project's various actions.

The Visual Corporate Image plays a vital role in shaping and defining the project's identity, providing a cohesive and consistent representation of SuPreAM. It is crucial to adhere to the elements specified in the VCI manual and use only authorized document templates. This approach ensures the accurate portrayal of the project's attributes and objectives, maintaining a consistent brand image.

The subsequent sections delineate various materials and elements that have been designed, encompassing the project's logo, templates, colours, fonts, and graphic elements. These components are intended for use and implementation in all communication and dissemination activities undertaken by all partners involved in the project.

10.1.1.1 SuPreAM logo

The logo stands as the most important and primary brand element within SuPreAM's visual identity and branding. Illustrated in Figure 5 below, the logo incorporates the project's acronym facilitating its recognition. Furthermore, the logo includes the main colours defined for the project that will be explained and described with more detail in following sections.

Figure 5: SuPreAM full colour version.

Various iterations of the logo have been crafted, including an inverse colour version, a positive and negative black and white version (to be used when colour application is restricted), and a black and white version tailored for use when no gradient is allowed. The preferred choice is the full-colour logo whenever possible. In instances where using the full-colour logo is not practical, it can be substituted with its black and white counterparts.

Figure 6: Full colour negative logo.

Figure 7: Black and white versions.

Figure 8: Grey logo maintaining the gradient.

Figure 9: SuPreAM logo adapted to different backgrounds.

10.1.1.2 Visual Corporate Identity Manual

Complementing the SuPreAM branding image, a visual identity and standards guidebook has been created and shared among partners to uphold the integrity of the project’s image and branding. This guidebook serves to ensure that all partners will use the elements properly, thereby conveying the characteristics and goals of the project consistently as a brand.

The visual identity manual serves as a comprehensive guide, clearly defining and detailing the proper utilization of identifying elements associated with SuPreAM. These elements encompass logos, colours, fonts, stationery and graphic resources.

Partners are encouraged to view the guidebook as a primary source for materials and instructions, serving as a foundation for the ongoing development of project-related materials. Subsequent sections herein provide a glimpse and description of certain aspects covered in the manual.

10.1.1.2.1 Fonts and corporate colours

As shown in the manual, two types of fonts have been defined to be used for project internal and external documents and materials. While “**Montserrat**” is established as the font for titles of promotional and advertising materials, “**Arial**” is the main font established for deliverables and other internal documents because it is a standard Microsoft Office typography included in Word and Power Point, among others.

All these types of fonts and its different versions (Regular, Light, Bold, Italic) are free and available in Google Fonts, so all partners can download them if necessary.

Figure 10: SuPreAM fonts for promotional materials (left) and for internal documents (right).

On the other hand, the VCI manual presents the SuPreAM colours palette to be implemented and used in all project's materials. According to this palette, the main colours are **fuchsia** (Pantone: #E517DE), **blue navy** (Pantone: #1D3ED0), **blue turquoise** (Pantone: #0EDDD7), **green lime** (Pantone: #63FE2D) and **black** (Pantone: #282828). The palette also includes a spectral gradient as shown in the image below.

Figure 11: SuPreAM corporate colours palette.

10.1.1.2.2 Stationery

The SuPreAM Visual Corporate Identity manual also details various elements prepared for stationery materials including letters, envelopes, business cards or digital supports. All these elements could be used by partners when it is needed.

Figure 12: Stationery elements designed for SuPreAM.

10.1.2 Project templates

At the beginning of the project, Eurecat has created different templates with the goal to uphold a unified and coherent image throughout the project's execution. These templates have been shared with all the consortium for a consistent use across all stages of the SuPreAM progress.

These templates include a PowerPoint template designed for both internal and external presentations, together with four distinct Word documents: one for deliverables, another for meeting agendas, a third for letters and a last one tailored for minutes.

10.1.2.1.1 Deliverable template

A Word document template has been created to be used for all the project's public and confidential deliverables. This document defines the use of a page header including the project's logo and the funding body's logo and a footer with some information about the document presented.

Figure 13: View of part of the SuPreAM deliverable template.

10.1.2.1.2 Agenda and meeting minutes template

These templates have been created to be used when preparing the agenda for internal consortium meetings or, if necessary, other kind of events, and for presenting the minutes and list of attendants. As in the other templates and project's documents, the agenda and minutes ones are based on the branding created and implemented within SuPreAM.

Figure 14: Agenda (left) and minutes (right) templates.

10.1.2.1.3 Letter template

This document is a template specifically prepared for letters that project’s partners may need to write during the SuPreAM execution.

Figure 15: SuPreAM letter template.

10.1.2.1.4 Power Point presentation

The Power Point template, to be used and implemented in all project’s internal and external presentations, includes a variety of slides with different options and designs to include the text and different visual elements to be used and adapted by all project’s partners when preparing a project’s presentation.

A screenshot of some slides is shown below:

Figure 16: View of SuPreAM presentation template.

10.2 Project public website

As defined in the project's work plan, Eurecat is the main responsible for designing, creating and executing the SuPreAM public website. Following the European Commission's recommendations, this website has been seamlessly incorporated into a designated URL hosted on Eurecat's own website.

Find the SuPreAM public website in this link: <https://eurecat.org/en/portfolio-items/supream/>

The sections hereinafter delineate the main features of the web platform, which will be positioned as the anchor for all communication activities associated with the project, serving as a centralised hub for all the public material of SuPreAM, including the main details of the project, available resources and public deliverables.

It's important to mention that the website's design is aligned with the SuPreAM corporate visual identity created by Eurecat and approved by all the consortium members. On the other hand, with the objective to ensure seamless browsing experience on smartphones, tablets and other devices, the website has been created and developed according to a responsive design approach. Regarding the website language, all the content is available in English.

Additionally, the website will be continuously updated showcasing the latest news, pertinent links to other relevant sites, published papers, and information on conferences and exhibitions participated throughout the project's duration.

10.2.1 Website structure

The suggested and implemented structure for the SuPreAM public website is depicted in the image below. As illustrated in the image, the website follows a one-page format indicating that the creation of other subpages linked to different sections is not incorporated into this plan.

Figure 17: SuPreAM website structure.

The purple sections indicate the parts included in the launch of the website, whereas the blue ones represent parts slated for development in subsequent stages, aligned with the progress of the project.

10.2.2 Website content

The subsequent sections outline the contents that have been published on the website at the time of its launch.

Initial Slider

The top of the page shows one slider with a title describing the project: “*SuPreAM project: Addressing finishing operations optimisation of Additive Manufactured (Amed) steel components via modelling*”.

SuPreAM in a nutshell

Boosting the implementation of Additive Manufacturing with optimal surface integrity.

About the project

The SuPreAM project is developing and improving the performance and capabilities of a predictive simulation model of finishing operations in steel Additive Manufacturing (AM).

SuPreAM has the objective to optimise the surface integrity of Additive Manufactured and Machined steel components and to reduce manufacturing expenditures at the steel industrial sector by minimising the material scrap and reducing the number of re-processing loops during finishing operations.

The excellence of SuPreAM relies on the integration of all the factors affecting surface integrity generation over additive manufactured workpieces in order to provide machining strategies solutions in the design stage, prior workpiece finishing, avoiding the generation of scrap, aiming to produce defect free components.

Key Data

- **Start-end date:** 1 July 2023 – 31 December 2026
- **Duration:** 42 months
- **Funder under:** Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS) programme of the European Union
- **Overall budget:** 1,565,380.41€
- **Reference number:** 101112346

SuPreAM pillars

SuPreAM integrates the influence of steels of manufacturing technologies and machining strategies in the development of the predictive models constituting a step forward for the identification of the main critical parameters affecting surface integrity.

- **Surface integrity prediction in machining/cutting/finishing processes:** integrating the influence of steels, of manufacturing technologies and of machining strategies in the development of the predictive models.
- **Modelling of machining/cutting/finishing processes:** developing the cutting process model using the Particle Finite Element Method (PFEM) which has shown promising results in the modelling of materials subjected to large deformation of the workpieces.
- **Machining of Additive Manufactured steels:** providing new insights into the cutting tool wear mechanisms behind surface integrity generation and identifying critical parameters on its generation.
- **Additive Manufacturing of novel maraging steel:** addressing the application of a new quality of steel that does not exist in the market.

Project phases

1. **Additive manufacturing of conventional and novel steels:** Improvement of machining operations through the study of the influence of AM process, steel microstructure, chemical composition, heat treatment and mechanical properties of AMed steel alloys.

2. **Machining strategies for Additive Manufactured steels:** Development of machining strategies, according to machining processes and finishing processes, with optimal surface integrity.
3. **Machining processes and component behaviour modelling:** Development of models of machining processes of AMed steels such as cutting machining modelling and numerical simulation.
4. **Surface integrity characterisation:** Evaluation of the machinability of the AM materials, considering steel quality, the AM process, heat treatment, cutting tool and/or post-processing parameters.
5. **Validation of the proposed solutions:** Demonstration of how two real components is suitable for being produced by Additive Manufacturing technologies and suitable for its use in real demanding application.

SuPreAM expected results

The SuPreAM project proposes the investigation in a holistic approach of the main factors affecting part quality of Additive Manufactured and Machined steel projects.

- To develop an in-house software module for the simulation of milling/turning and finishing processes based on particle finite element method (PFEM).
- To evaluate steel grades for surface integrity optimisation of AMed and machined parts.
- To develop an in-house software module for the simulation of the electrical discharge machining (EDM) process.
- To determine the influence of steel AM technology, machining strategies, machining process parameters and cutting tools materials.
- To identify and describe the most significant AMed and machined component characteristics and to establish surface integrity and functionality relationship.

Consortium

SuPreAM is a collaborative project with a multidisciplinary team with different capacities and knowledge in disciplines ranging from advanced characterisation, materials performance, simulation, machining processes, advanced testing and modelling, and Metal Additive Manufacturing.

The consortium of the SuPreAM project, coordinated by Eurecat Technology Centre, is formed by 7 partners from Spain, Portugal and Sweden.

Eurecat

Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The centre offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to SuPreAM

Eurecat is in charge of coordinating the project through the Metallic and Ceramic Materials Unit, which is focused on the investigation of the relation between the microstructure and tribomechanical properties of materials and the optimization of the forming processes to obtain materials with improved characteristics. Within SuPreAM project, Eurecat takes the responsibility to the investigation in surface integrity characterization of additive manufactured and machined components, tribological, mechanical and micromechanical behaviour of materials, performance of cutting tools and hard coatings. Moreover, the centre is also responsible for managing the project's communication and dissemination activities.

CIMNE

The Centre Internacional de Mètodes Numèrics en Enginyeria (CIMNE) was established in 1987 to advance the fields of engineering and applied sciences through the innovative application of numerical methods and computational techniques. Collaboratively formed with the support of the Government of Catalonia and UNESCO, CIMNE operates in close association with the Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya (UPC). CIMNE has strategically positioned itself on a global stage, aiming to become a frontrunner in computational mechanics. In 2019, CIMNE received the esteemed recognition of being accredited as a Severo Ochoa Center of Excellence by the Spanish Ministry of Science.

CIMNE's core focus is on computational mechanics, underpinned by a commitment to research, knowledge dissemination, and the practical application of numerical methods in engineering. As it moves forward, CIMNE envisions a future where it leads on a global scale in groundbreaking research pertaining to computational models in engineering. Their overarching goal is to develop pioneering numerical technologies capable of addressing contemporary and future societal challenges. In essence, CIMNE aspires to be at the forefront of innovation in the realm of computational mechanics and beyond, contributing significantly to the advancement of science and engineering.

Contribution to SuPreAM

CIMNE plays a pivotal role in the project, with a central focus on leading WP4 dedicated to machining and surface finishing modelling. In WP4, CIMNE undertakes a multifaceted role, coordinating project activities, setting research priorities, and overseeing the development and validation of models for various machining processes, including milling, turning, and EDM. Their responsibilities extend to the implementation of critical components such as thermoplastic material models, friction characteristics, tool-wear laws, and surface roughness models, ensuring the accuracy and applicability of the numerical simulations.

CIMNE's expertise also encompasses the development of user-friendly software tailored for numerical modelling and simulation of machining processes. This specialized software aims to achieve high-quality surface integrity in additive manufactured and machined steel components, addressing the project's core objectives.

Grupo Sevilla Control (GSC)

Grupo Sevilla Control (GSC) is a global Aerospace Tier 2 for Machined parts & Assembly through its 35 CNC and auxiliary machinery. GSC focuses its productive activity on the manufacture of integral solutions for structures and AOG, mainly in metallic materials. All of

this in a full range of aerospace material, being focused on but not limited on Medium bench size(100-400mm) and Titanium, Aluminium and Steel as main materials.

Contribution to SuPreAM

GSC is going to lead the integration of machining strategies developed to analyse and improve machinability of additive manufacturing steel for aeronautical sector. For that, GSC will be in charge of defining the aeronautical case taking into account requirements of the candidates and constrains of additive technology. In addition, GSC cope the definition of machining and process conditions of sample parts with the model validation for simulation in contrast with the real conditions and parameters.

DRT Rapid

DRT Rapid is part of a group of companies (DRT Group) with competences in different areas related to the production of moulds and plastics. The company is dedicated to the production of moulds and special tools for different industries (automotive, health, cosmetics, construction, etc.), exporting 100% of its products mainly to the German and Spanish markets.

There is a complementarity of skills in the DRT Group that allows the entire value chain of the plastic part to be covered. The evolution of DRT RAPID has been marked by a clear progression in the value chain, increasingly assuming the stages of engineering, design and prototyping, migrating to the position of product development partner. The R&D activities allowed to provide customers innovative and competitive solutions, strengthening the position as a development partner with a clear approach to the final customer (OEM). The company's main customers are the main automotive industry brands such as Peugeot, Volkswagen, Audi, Mercedes and Porsche. DRT RAPID is one in a few Portuguese mould companies working directly with OEM, namely with the VW and BMW Group. Recently it had the classification B (2nd level of the scale) attributed in an audit done by the VW Group. Member of the VW Autoeuropa Suppliers Club.

Contribution to SuPreAM

DRT RAPID will participate in the project leading one work package focused on machining and finishing processes and strategies. DRT RAPID will give its expertise in 3D printing (DMLS) and machining and finishing processes of steel parts with the focus in the moulds industry.

Luleå University of Technology

LTU is the northern-most technical university in Sweden. The research subject Solid Mechanics at the department of Engineering Sciences and Mathematics will carry out the research within this project. The department has about 220 employees and a turnover of more than 25 MEUR/year.

Research is about 75% of this and most of it is financed via external funds (2/3). The research within Solid Mechanics is focusing on the use and development of advanced finite element simulations and material models. The group has been active within the field of simulation of manufacturing for more than three decades. It is world leading in the field of simulation of

welding/metal deposition and machining but also other manufacturing processes are modelled.

Contribution to SuPreAM

LTU participates in the project as leader of one work package focused on surface integrity and functionality relationship. LTU is also involved in model development for machining processes of AMed steels to predict surface integrity and perform injection mould and structural component behaviour simulation and validation. Further, LTU conducts experimental material testing for calibration of thermoplastic material models of AMed steels.

IDONIAL

Fundación IDONIAL is a Spanish, private, independent, non-profit, multisectorial technology centre which contributes to the promotion and development of the business fabric in its areas of technological specialization. IDONIAL offers integral tailored solutions in the entire value chain, related to materials, advanced manufacturing and digital industry through technology development and innovation.

IDONIAL, thanks to its staff of 160 workers with extensive experience in different sectors is involved in more than 70 new R&D projects every year, 500 Technical assistances and 6000 technological services. IDONIAL has wide experience both as partners and as coordinators in EU research programmes (H2020, FP, EUREKA, Era-Nets and INTERREG). It actively participates in several European Technology Platforms and belongs to the governing bodies of the Additive Manufacturing and Nanotechnology innovation ones.

Contribution to SuPreAM

IDONIAL participates in the project as leader of one work package focused on the definition of requirements, AM materials and process-chain implementation. In general, IDONIAL is active in all about Additive Manufacturing (SLM) of samples and parts, post processing heat treatment optimization, microstructure, basic and in use properties validation (bulk properties).

ArcelorMittal

ArcelorMittal (AMMR) is the world's leading steel and mining company. It has steel manufacturing in 16 countries and customers in 155 countries. ArcelorMittal has a large offer (more than 200 trademark products) representing ~62.9MTon of steel shipments in 2021. Moreover, the group holds more than 724 patent families and has launched 51 new products and solutions in 2021. This is supported by a workforce of around 1,500 full-time researchers at 11 geographical sites throughout the world, with centres strategically placed in Europe, North and South America and close to key operations and customers.

News & Events

A section showcasing articles that spotlight the main advancements and results of the SuPreAM project. It also includes content related to project meetings and articles authored by partners on subjects related to the project.

This section will also include a schedule detailing upcoming events where the SuPreAM consortium will be involved, whether as organisers, attendees or participants. Furthermore, a compilation of articles connected to these events will be made available.

Finally, within this section present notable project events, such as the different webinars and workshops to be organised, will be promoted and announced. After the event celebration, downloadable resources like presentations and documents shared will be available, along with the video recording of the event.

Resources

This section will be continuously updated with all the public materials of the project, including visual materials, public deliverables, scientific production, and media features. Specific sections for each type of content have been created for a correct visualisation.

Main outcomes

- Deliverables: publication of all the public reports for in-depth access to project outputs.
- Promotional materials: SuPreAM communication and promotional materials produced (rollup, trifold, posters, etc.).
- Scientific production: scientific articles related to the project's research and published in open access journals or as conference proceedings.
- Media impacts: list of the main articles featuring the project published in generalist and specialised media outlets.

Contact information

A section with the main contact details allowing visitors to contact the project's coordinator and send comments and questions. The section shows the project's email supream.project@gmail.com, controlled by Eurecat to manage all information and feedback received.

The SuPreAM project proposes the investigation in a holistic approach of the main factors affecting part quality of Additive Manufactured and Machined steel projects.

- To develop an in-house software module for the simulation of milling/turning and finishing processes based on particle finite element method (PFEM).
- To evaluate steel grades for surface integrity optimisation of AMed and machined parts.
- To develop an in-house software module for the simulation of the electrical discharge machining (EDM) process.
- To determine the influence of steel AM technology, machining strategies, machining process parameters and cutting tools materials.
- To identify and describe the most significant AMed and machined component characteristics and to establish surface integrity and functionality relationship.

CONSORTIUM

SuPreAM is a collaborative project with a multidisciplinary team with different capacities and knowledge in disciplines ranging from **advanced characterisation, materials performance, simulation, machining processes, advanced testing and modelling, and Metal Additive Manufacturing.**

The consortium of the SuPreAM project, coordinated by Eurecat Technology Centre, is formed by **7 partners from Spain, Portugal and Sweden.**

- Eurecat
- CIMNE
- Grupo Sevilla Control (GSC)
- DRT Rapid
- Luleå University of Technology (LTU)
- IDONIAL
- ArcelorMittal

Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The centre offers to their Innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to SuPreAM

Eurecat is in charge of coordinating the project through the Metallic and Ceramic Materials Unit, which is focused on the investigation of the relation between the microstructure and tribomechanical properties of materials and the optimization of the forming processes to obtain materials with improved characteristics. Within SuPreAM project, Eurecat takes the responsibility to the investigation in surface integrity characterization of additive manufactured and machined components, tribological, mechanical and micromechanical behaviour of materials, performance of cutting tools and hard coatings. Moreover, the centre is also responsible for managing the project's communication and dissemination activities.

- Twitter
- LinkedIn
- Facebook
- YouTube

NEWS & EVENTS

26
10, 2023

Six RFCS projects coordinated by Eurecat presented at the SteelTech Congress
October 26th, 2023

Eurecat has participated as exhibitor of the Steel Tech 2023 this week in Bilbao Exhibition Center from October 25-27. Amongst the center capacities in the steel sector, information on six Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS)-funded projects COOPHS, HELIX, SupreAM, NewAIMS, Sup3rForm and MIPRE was displayed and presented. [...]

3
10, 2023

Optimising surface finish in additive manufacturing in the steel industry to reduce defects and manufacturing costs
October 3rd, 2023

The European SuPreAM project is built on integrating all the aspects affecting the surface integrity of additively manufactured parts. It is to develop predictive models which factor in the influence of additive manufacturing technology, steel grades, machining strategies and process parameters plus component surface properties. A plastic injection mould [...]

14
07, 2023

SuPreAM project kicks-off!
July 14th, 2023

The SuPreAM project has kicked off in July 2023 with the objective to address finishing operations optimisation of Additive Manufactured (AMed) steel components via modelling. Coordinated by Eurecat, the project has the ambition to optimise the surface integrity of Additive Manufactured and Machined steel components and to reduce manufacturing expenditures [...]

RESOURCES

> Deliverables

Project materials

Media impacts

Here is a list of SuPreAM work packages and deliverables.

WP1 – Project Coordination

- D1.1 – Comprehensive overview of the project
- D1.2 – Risk assessment and contingency plan
- D1.3 – Communication and dissemination plan
- D1.4 – Public publishable report

WP2 – Definition of requirements, AM materials and process-chain implementation

- D2.1 – Software GUI design and material databases requirements
- D2.2 – Production and quality assurance of samples for machining and surface characterization

WP3 – Machining and finishing processes and strategies

- D3.1 – Definition of machining and finishing strategies
- D3.2 – Machined and finished sample parts

WP4 – Machining and surface finishing modelling

CONTACT US

To contact with SuPreAM team please fill contact us by clicking the button below. We will get in touch with you as soon as possible.

CONTACT US

Figure 18: View of the SuPreAM website design.

10.2.3 Layout

As detailed in previous sections, the SuPreAM website embraces a one-page layout without a standalone menu, necessitating users to navigate through scrolling. Nevertheless, individual articles crafted to communicate updates on project activities will feature dedicated pages for each post. The primary website will exhibit article titles and main images.

Both the header and footer areas prominently present Eurecat's information, seamlessly integrating the SuPreAM page into the overarching website of the technology centre. A separate footer has been developed to acknowledge the project's funding. This section presents the following text, accompanied by the EU flag:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS): project num. 101112346. This document reflects only SuPreAM consortium view and neither the European Commission or any associated parties are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

10.2.4 Managing and updating

Eurecat, as the main responsible of the communication tasks, has taken on the responsibility of developing and implementing the SuPreAM website, including the site hosting and configuration tasks.

Moreover, Eurecat has the role of overseeing the maintenance of the site, consistently adding new content, and ensuring continuous update. The website has been optimised for Search Engine Optimisation (SEO), ensuring favourable positioning in search results.

It is planned to regularly update the project website by the publication of new content and information each time a new dissemination action will be done, a goal or result will be achieved or there is other type of news worth publishing. This dynamic approach guarantees that the website stays an up-to-date and all-encompassing resource for information related to the project and updates on its progress. All the content published will be based on project partners inputs as did previously while launching the website.

10.2.5 Data protection & website analytics

With the objective to ensure compliance with the GDPR, the SuPreAM website is compliant with all the European data protection standards and requirements. Therefore, the website has been conscientiously adjusted to align with the most recent directives set forth by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) in July 2020. These directives, implemented and effective since October 31st 2020, aim to harmonize cookie installation practices with the consent requirements outlined in the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Following the currently AEPD "Guidelines on the Use of Cookies", explicit consent for cookies must be obtained through actions such as clicking "*I accept*" or engaging in similar affirmative gestures. Passive activities like browsing or using the scroll bar are deemed insufficient for

consent. Furthermore, the utilisation of cookie walls without offering alternative consent options is deemed unacceptable.

Eurecat, as the proprietor of the website and in adherence to the latest directives from AEPD, has introduced a cookies banner. This banner enables users to make informed decisions regarding the installation of non-essential cookies. By aligning with this updated regulation, web analytics will only be monitored for users who consent to such cookies. This may potentially lead to a reduction in certain statistical data associated with website visits, page views and user counts.

It's important to mention that users maintain the flexibility to review and modify their cookie preferences at any time, as the Cookies Setting Banner remains accessible at the bottom right corner of the page. Moreover, the website dedicates specific pages to provide detailed information on the [privacy policy](#), [cookies policy](#) and [legal disclaimer](#).

The SuPreAM public website features a form specifically crafted for handling user inquiries, with Eurecat serving as the data controller for this form. The information gathered through the contact form will be shared with project partners to ensure precise and effective responses to user inquiries.

Finally, in terms of website analytics, it has been integrated Google Analytics 4 to systematically monitor website traffic and generate periodic reports on the site's performance. This functionality empowers the project team to glean insights into visitor interactions and assess the overall effectiveness of web pages, as well as to periodically monitor and analyse the SuPreAM webpage related KPIs (*detailed in section 3.3.2 KPIs*).

10.3 Project promotional materials

10.3.1 General digital and printed materials

With the aim to assist in the dissemination activities of the project different promotional materials have been designed and produced including a rollup, a flyer and a poster layout. It is ensured that all these materials strictly adhere to the guidelines outlined in the project's visual identity manual.

These materials are accessible and downloadable to all consortium members for their use and additionally, publicly available on the project's website, enhancing the SuPreAM reach and visibility. Promotional materials will be regularly updated according to the main project's achievements and milestones or upon partners' request.

10.3.1.1 Rollup and flyer

Two different versions of a project rollup and a trifold have been produced to be used when attending and presenting SuPreAM in dissemination events such as congresses, conferences and fairs, among others.

Figure 19: View of the SuPreAM rollups

Figure 20: View of the SuPreAM trifold.

10.3.1.2 Poster layout

The poster layout is a Power Point document presenting a structure proposal to include different contents and information of the project. This document can serve as a template to be used and adapted by all partners when preparing a project's poster for presenting it in a specific event.

As illustrated in the image below, the document includes guidelines on how to structure the content and information along the poster.

Header			Author names Company name, full address E-mail: supream.project@gmail.com
Introduction	<p>Predictive simulation of finishing operations in steel Additive Manufacturing for optimal surface integrity</p> <p>Poster title: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.</p>		<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer eleifend iaculis laoreet. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida vehicula non id magna. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer eleifend iaculis laoreet. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus.</p> <p><i> Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.</i></p>
Methodology	<p>Title methodology section</p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer eleifend iaculis laoreet. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida vehicula non id magna.</p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer eleifend iaculis laoreet. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida vehicula non id magna. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida vehicula non id magna.</p>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Insert image / graph</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Insert image / graph</div>	
Results	<p>Title results section</p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer eleifend iaculis laoreet. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida vehicula non id magna.</p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer eleifend iaculis laoreet. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida vehicula non id magna.</p>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Space for an image / graph</div> <p>HIGHLIGHTED SENTENCE: Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet. Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet.</p>	
Conclusions	<p>Title conclusions section</p> <p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer eleifend iaculis laoreet. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus. Phasellus non massa at dolor gravida vehicula non id magna.</p>	<p>Lorem ipsum dolor sit amet, consectetur adipiscing elit. Integer eleifend iaculis laoreet. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus. Duis et dolor aliquet, commodo velit eu, sodales metus.</p>	
References	<p>Project partner logos and references. If needed please also referent collaborating entities.</p> <p><small>This project has received funding from the European Union's Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFSR) project/num: 101112248. This document reflects only SuPreAM contribution and neither the European Commission nor RFSR project partners are responsible for any view that may be made of the information it contains.</small></p> <p>www.eurecat.org/en/portfolio-item/supream</p>		

Figure 21: SuPreAM poster layout.

10.3.2 Audiovisual materials

Recognizing the effectiveness of videos in conveying project achievements and results to a wider audience, a video will be produced at the end of the project and uploaded on partners' YouTube channels to increase its impact. The primary aim of this video is to effectively communicate the goals and results of SuPreAM to a broad audience, utilizing the visual medium to enhance understanding and engagement. Additionally, this video will be used, if necessary, in events and will be accessible after the project's end.

The video will be produced following the main guidelines defined in the SuPreAM branding manual and will have a clear reference to European Commission support via the RFCS program.

- **Project final video (M42):** Eurecat will prepare and produce a video compiling the results, milestones and achievements of the project, as well as its applications and its benefits. It will include images on the work and research done.

If necessary, the production of other audio-visual materials will be evaluated among the consortium ensuring flexibility and responsiveness to emerging opportunities for effective communication.

10.4 Social Media

The SuPreAM project will have also presence in the different Social Media corporate partners accounts with the objective to promote and communicate the main achievements, milestones and dissemination actions and to engage with relevant stakeholders interested in the project.

At this sense, all partners have the mission to contribute spreading the word through their personal, but especially corporate, Social Media channels mainly Twitter and LinkedIn, but also Facebook or Instagram, if applicable.

Partners have the objective to publish **a minimum of 50 posts on LinkedIn** and **a minimum of 30 on Twitter** during all the project's execution. As shown in Figure 24, at the end of December 2023 (M6), **3 posts have been published** communicating different news about the project.

Eurecat, as the project's coordinator and dissemination task responsible, will have the responsibility of notifying the EC about possible content of interest to be published through its official Social Media channels.

Table 3: Project partners corporate social media accounts.

PARTNER	LinkedIn	Twitter	YouTube
EUT	https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/	@Eurecat_news	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWeVIFJ_t6ozc7bDaKZw https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/
CIMNE	https://www.linkedin.com/company/cimne	@cimne	https://www.youtube.com/@CIMNEMC
IDONIAL	https://www.linkedin.com/company/idonial/	@idonialtech	NA

GSC	https://es.linkedin.com/company/gsc-aero	NA	https://www.youtube.com/@gscsevillaccontrol8582
DRT	https://www.linkedin.com/company/drt-group	@GroupDrt	https://www.youtube.com/@drtgroup1456
ARCELOR	https://www.linkedin.com/company/arcelormittal/	NA	NA
LTU	https://www.linkedin.com/school/ulea-university-of-technology	@LTUniv	https://www.youtube.com/c/ltuse

The influence of SuPreAM partners on social media networks is set to extend to over 781,000 followers on LinkedIn, surpassing 22,000 on Twitter, and garnering more than 4,000 subscribers on YouTube.

Table 4: Followers and subscribers on Social Media partners accounts.

PARTNER	LinkedIn followers	Twitter followers	YouTube subscribers
EUT	30,000	16,500	2,260
CIMNE	5,707	2,352	2,550
IDONIAL	4,252	858	NA
GSC	4,315	NA	10
DRT	3,863	17	37
ARCELOR	697,080	NA	NA
LTU	56,861	4,970	1,460

10.4.1 Manual and guidelines for publishing about SuPreAM on Social Media

With the goal to increase the reach of the Social Media publications, partners have been encouraged to frequently use the following hashtags, commonly used in other areas within the project's scope, and relevant handles. This strategy aims to maximise the impact when sharing project news or information about results.

Figure 22: List of relevant handles to mention.

- #SuPreAM
- #SuPreAMProject
- #RFCS
- #Steel
- #AdditiveManufacturing
- #steelmaking
- #metals
- #innovation
- #HorizonEU
- #EUGreenDeal
- #MaterialsScience
- #cleansteel
- #steeltransition
- #industry
- #circulartransition
- #climate
- #EUfunding
- #PredictiveSimulation
- #Decarbonisation
- #MaterialsScience
- #PFEM
- #materials

Figure 23: Initial list of relevant hashtags to include in Social Media publications.

Figure 24: Some examples of SuPreAM posts published on Social Media.

Eurecat has created a periodic content plan, which has been shared with all the partners, with a proposal of messages covering different topics and encouraging partners to publish diverse content through their corporate and personal Social Media channels.

The first battery of social media posts, marking the project's debut on social media platforms, is designed to elevate awareness and channel traffic to the official website. These posts are meticulously crafted to communicate the project's objectives, milestones, and notable aspects effectively. The intention is to foster engagement and interest among the target audience while promoting the project website.

Tweets proposal

The #SuPreAM project, participated by [NAME COMPANY], aims to optimize the surface integrity of #AdditiveManufactured and #MachinedSteel components to reduce manufacturing expenditures at the #steel industrial sector

Learn more ► <https://cutt.ly/SuPreAM>

We are launching the #RFCS #SuPreAMproject, addressing finishing operations optimisation of #AdditiveManufactured #steel components via modelling

@Eurecat_news @cimne @GroupDrt @idonialtech @LTUniv #GSC #ArcelorMittal

<https://cutt.ly/SuPreAM>

[NAME COMPANY] participates in #SuPreAM #RFCS project, boosting the implementation of #AdditiveManufacturing with optimal surface integrity

Learn more about the project ↪
<https://cutt.ly/SuPreAM>

LinkedIn posts proposal

We are launching the #RFCS #SuPreAMProject, with the objective to optimise the surface integrity of #AdditiveManufactured and Machined #steel components and to reduce manufacturing expenditures at the steel industrial sector by minimising the material scrap and reducing the number of re-processing loops during finishing operations.

#EUFunding #EUProjects #SteelIndustry #Innovation

The project, coordinated by @Eurecat – Technology Centre of Catalonia, is participated by @Cimne @GroupDrt @idonialtech @LTUniv @GSC-acero y @ArcelorMittal

<https://cutt.ly/SuPreAM>

The #SuPreAMproject, participated by [NAME OF YOUR COMPANY] is developing new predictive and optimisation models for surface finishing operations to drive additive manufacturing in the industrial steel sector and reduce defects and manufacturing costs which will also help to minimise scrap.

#RFCSProgramme #EUFunding #EUGreenDeal

The project, coordinated by @Eurecat – Technology Centre of Catalonia, is participated by @Cimne @GroupDrt @idonialtech @LTUniv @GSC-acero y @ArcelorMittal

<https://cutt.ly/SuPreAM>

10.5 Media relations

Press releases production is an effective strategy to communicate on project's milestones, achievements and impacts to academia and industry stakeholders but also to a more general and non-specialised public. Taking this into account, during the project **at least two press releases are scheduled**, one already produced (M3) and another one by the end of the project (M42).

All press releases will be disseminated to partners in English for feedback, allowing them to adapt the content to their corporate language and share it with their regional media contacts as needed. Besides the consortium press releases, country-focused press releases oriented to a specific stakeholder group may be prepared by partners, always informing the project coordinator and communication responsible (Eurecat).

The press releases production will cover a range of subjects, encompassing the revelation of research findings, attainment of project milestones, updates on meetings, participation in or hosting of events, and other notable initiatives.

As part of the project a media outlets database will be created, and continuously reviewed and updated, with a list of specialised media covering Additive Manufacturing, automotive, steel components, materials performance, machining processes and advanced testing, among other project-related topics. **Throughout the project a minimum of 5 publications in key specialised media and 10 in general outlets are expected.**

An initial list of European and international specialised media outlets identified as relevant to promote SuPreAM outputs is included below:

Table 5: Initial list of specialised media outlets for SuPreAM.

Media outlet	Website	Language
Automotive Manufacturing Solutions	https://www.automotivemanufacturingsolutions.com/	English
3Dnatives	https://www.3dnatives.com/es/	Spanish
Additive Manufacturing Media	https://www.additivemanufacturing.media/	English
Revista Metalmecánica	https://www.metalmecanica.com/es/revista-digital?items_per_page=9	Spanish
Metal AM	https://www.metal-am.com/	English
Materials Today	https://www.materialstoday.com/	English
Car Magazine	https://www.carmagazine.co.uk/electric/	English
Revista Interempresas Automoción	https://www.interempresas.net/Sector-Automocion/Articulos/	Spanish
Steel International	https://www.steeltimesint.com/	English
La Tribuna de Automoción	https://www.latribunadeautomocion.es/	Spanish

10.5.1 Press releases production and calendar

Since the beginning of the project (M1 – M6), SuPreAM communication and dissemination leader Eurecat has produced **two press releases**. The first one prepared in collaboration with all the consortium and offering general information about the project, partners involved and expected outcomes. Another press release has been prepared informing about the presentation of different RFCS projects showcased in the SteelTech Congress celebrated on October 2023

- **September 2023 – Optimising surface finish in additive manufacturing in the steel industry to reduce defects and manufacturing costs.** Read the full text [here](#).
- **October 2023 – Eurecat leads three European projects that drive the optimisation of steel components and the decarbonisation of their manufacturing process.** Read the full text (in Catalan and Spanish) [here](#).

The screenshot shows the website page for the press release titled "Optimising surface finish in additive manufacturing in the steel industry to reduce defects and manufacturing costs". The main visual is a 3D surface topography plot of a square part, showing a complex, textured surface with a color gradient from blue to red. The page includes a navigation bar with the Eurecat logo and various menu items. A "Recent" news section on the right lists three articles with their respective dates. A search bar is located at the bottom right of the page.

Figure 25: View of the SuPreAM press release published at the website.

[Eurecat](#) / [Àmbits de Coneixement](#) / [Sectors](#) / [Serveis](#) / [Labs](#) / [Projectes](#) / [Talent](#) / [Actualitat](#) / [Contacte](#) / [in](#) / [yt](#) / [fb](#) / [ca](#) / [q](#)

Eurecat lidera tres projectes europeus que impulsen l'optimització de components d'acer i la descarbonització del seu procés de fabricació

Pàgina inicial / Automoció/Materials Metàl·lics i Ceràmics/Notes de premsa / **Eurecat lidera tres projectes europeus que impulsen l'optimització de components d'acer i la descarbonització del seu procés de fabricació**

Eurecat lidera tres projectes europeus que impulsen l'optimització de components d'acer i la descarbonització del seu procés de fabricació

El centre tecnològic Eurecat lidera tres projectes europeus amb un pressupost total de 6,9 milions d'euros, que impulsen l'optimització de diferents qualitats d'acer per millorar-ne les seves propietats i usos en sectors com els de l'automoció i l'aeronàutic, alhora que busquen aconseguir una reducció de defectes, despeses de manufactura i emissions de diòxid de carboni en la seva fabricació, incrementant la descarbonització de la indústria.

Les iniciatives es mostren aquesta setmana a la fira Steel Tech 2023, l'esdeveniment de referència del sud d'Europa per al sector del metall que reuneix els principals agents de la cadena de valor i se celebra a Bilbao del 25 al 27 d'octubre.

En concret, Eurecat coordina el **consorci europeu COOPHS**, que treballa per millorar la producció d'acer amb baixes emissions de CO₂ per al sector de l'automoció, mitjançant el desenvolupament de processos de fabricació més sostenibles que contribuiran a la seva descarbonització.

"La producció d'acer d'alt rendiment per la via del reciclatge permetrà minimitzar les emissions de CO₂ de la indústria automobilística, així com avançar en la sostenibilitat i la competitivitat del mercat europeu de l'acer, en línia amb els objectius del Fons de recerca per al carbó i l'acer (RFCS) i el Pacte Verd Europeu", assenyala el coordinador del projecte i cap de la Línia de Nous Processos per a Materials Avançats de la Unitat de Materials Metàl·lics i Ceràmics d'Eurecat, Jaume Pujante.

Segueix-nos a les xarxes socials!

[X](#) [yt](#) [in](#)

Recent Q

 Assagen nous processos d'impressió 3D d'acers d'alt rendiment
desembre 13th, 2023

 Eurecat desenvolupa un nou tipus d'interfície intel·ligent ultrafina per a la nova generació d'automòbils
desembre 11th, 2023

 European consortium to promote new additive manufacturing processes of optimized high-performance steels
novembre 30th, 2023

Buscar

Figure 26: View of the Catalan press release published in Eurecat's website.

10.5.2 Media articles featuring SuPreAM

As a consequence of press releases production and media relations activities, SuPreAM project has been featured in a total of **8 articles including general and specialised media outlets** at local and national level. As stated in the clipping tool these media actions have reached over 3M people.

In the following table it can be seen the details of these articles:

Table 6: SuPreAM clipping (M1 – M6).

Media	Title	Date	Type	Language	Link
Interempresas MetalMecánica	Eurecat lidera la optimización de componentes de acero y la descarbonización de su fabricación	14.11.2023	Online	Spanish	Link
HispaRob	Eurecat lidera tres proyectos europeos que impulsan la optimización de componentes de acero y la descarbonización de su proceso de fabricación	13.11.2023	Online	Spanish	Link
Industry Talks	Eurecat lidera tres proyectos europeos para optimizar la producción de acero disminuyendo la huella de carbono	26.10.2023	Online	Spanish	Link
Metales & Máquinas	Eurecat lidera tres proyectos europeos que impulsan la optimización de componentes de acero	26.10.2023	Online	Spanish	Link
Regió 7	Eurecat Manresa lidera 3 projectes amb 6,9 milions de pressupost	26.10.2023	Online	Catalan	Link
Regió 7	Eurecat Manresa lidera 3 projectes amb 6,9 milions de pressupost	26.10.2023	Print	Catalan	Link
Nació Manresa	Eurecat Manresa lidera tres proejctes europeus que impulsen l'optimització de components d'hacer	25.10.2023	Online	Catalan	Link
Solar News	Eurecat lidera tres proyectos europeos que impulsan la optimización de componentes de acero y la descarbonización de su proceso de fabricación	25.10.2023	Online	Spanish	Link

11. Dissemination activities

11.1 Key conferences, congresses, exhibitions and other events

Participating in national and international conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and workshops aimed at both academia and the industrial community is crucial for transferring the knowledge acquired during the project. Various events provide suitable platforms for showcasing and publishing the results of SuPreAM covering a broad spectrum of topics related to the project. By participating in academic and industrial events SuPreAM partners will be able to establish connections within the sector (OEMs, Tier 1, Tier 2 companies), as well as with peer researchers.

This kind of dissemination activity will be mainly focused on the partners' countries but the attendance in events taking place in other European countries will be also considered and evaluated, especially if these events are targeted to communities strongly related to the project activities.

During the internal progress report meetings, partners will discuss about the participation in academic and industrial events trying to find the best way and strategy to showcase the results and outputs of the project.

As explained in the section 3.3.1. *Reporting of communication and dissemination activities*, the Dissemination Tracker Excel file will be available for partners to note their confirmed, planned or done activities, as well as to identify future events of special interest.

11.1.1 Events participation

In the following table, a non-exhaustive initial list of events already identified is displayed:

Table 7: List of identified conferences, fairs and exhibitions of interest for SuPreAM project.

EVENT NAME	TYPE	DATE	CITY	COUNTRY
Particle Methods and Applications Conference	Conference	January 2023	Santa Fe	USA
Smart Manufacturing World Summit	Conference	April 2023	Stuttgart	Germany
Advanced Factories	Exhibition & congress	April 2024	Barcelona	Spain
CIRP Conference on Surface Integrity	Conference	May 2024	Bremen	Germany
World Cutting Tool Conference	Conference	May 2024	Osaka	Japan
CHS2 International Conference on	Conference	May 2024	Nashville	USA

Hot Sheet Metal Forming of High-Performance Steel				
ICPTDP 2024: International Conference on 3D Printing Technologies and Digital Printing	Conference	June 2024	Oslo	Norway
3D Print Congress & Exhibition	Congress & Exhibition	2024 (To determine)	Paris	France
BIEMH	Exhibition	June 2024	Bilbao	Spain
FEMS Junior EUROMAT 2024	Conference	July 2024	Manchester	UK
Formnext	Exhibition	November 2024	Frankfurt	Germany
Advanced Manufacturing Congress	Congress	November 2024	Madrid	Spain
CIRP Conference on Modelling and Machining Operations	Conference	May 2025	Mons	Belgium
European Cutting Tool Association (ECTA) Conference	Conference	May 2025	To determine	To determine
EMO Hannover	Exhibition	September 2025	Hannover	Germany
SteelTech Congress	Congress	October 2025	Bilbao	Spain
CHS2 Congress	Conference	June/July 2026	TBD	TBD
SteelTech Congress	Congress	October 2026	TBD	TBD

From M1 – M6, partners from Eurecat, the project’s coordinator, have effectively presented SuPreAM during a key congress of the steel industry sector, signifying the first project participation in relevant conferences and exhibitions.

- **SteelTech Exhibition (Bilbao, Spain), 25th – 27th of October 2023.**

SuPreAM coordinator, Eurecat, attended as exhibitor the SteelTech 2023 celebrated at the Bilbao Exhibition Center from October 25-27.

In this activity, SuPreAM was presented together with other Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS)-funded projects coordinated by Eurecat: HELIX, COOPHS, NewAIMS, Sup3rForm and MiPRE.

Figure 27: Eurecat partners at the stand showcased in the Steel Tech Exhibition.

11.1.2 Workshops and webinars organisation

As part of the project, different workshops and webinars will be organised with the objective to involve other relevant stakeholders and transfer SuPreAM research results and outcomes, as well as exploring and developing future ideas for cooperation. Partners will collectively discuss and decide whether to host the events in one of the consortium countries, online or as part of a prominent congress or conference.

Workshops will be announced through the project's communication channels (public website and Social Media partners channels) to have a significant number of stakeholders attending them. If necessary, the sessions will be recorded, and recordings will be shared with all the registrants and attendees.

Partners will work to gather **more than 30 attendees for each of the organized webinars and workshops**. Although the events will be open to all interested parties and widely promoted through the project's communication tools, partners will also send private invitations to key contacts.

As detailed in the Table 8, the webinar expected by M42 will be organised as the final event of SuPreAM to publicly present the project results to key actors from academia, scientific and industrial communities.

More details, a proposal title and tentative date are listed below:

Table 8: Webinars and workshops proposed details.

Proposed topic/title	Leading partner	Place	Tentative date
Webinar #1: Optimizing Surface Integrity in Additive Manufacturing and Machining Processes	EUT	Manresa / Online	M21
Webinar #2: Finishing operations in steel additive manufactured components	AMIII	Avilés / Online	M36
Webinar #3: SuPreAM Final Event - Promoting the optimization of steel components	EUT	Manresa / Online	M42

11.2 Training activities

SuPreAM partners aim to integrate the gained knowledge in at least 2 current training programmes throughout and post the project. This initiative seeks to transfer expertise to companies, research centres, and European SMEs operating in the project's domains. In addition, the partners will actively disseminate, as mentioned above, project outcomes within the scientific, educational, and business communities, laying the groundwork for further exploitation.

Training activities will be mostly carried out during the 3rd year of the project by universities and research centres involved in the project's consortium (LTU, CMNE, EUT).

The training actions are focused both at the academic/scientific community and industry professionals. Moreover, they will also target members within project partners' organisations for a horizontal knowledge transfer.

Training activities will be done in a series of formats, including project results and materials into undergraduate, master or PhD programmes, specialised courses, open days or online tutorials, among other kind of actions.

11.3 Clustering activities

During all the implementation of the SuPreAM project, partners will uphold ongoing communication with coordinators of interconnected projects, pertinent industry associations, companies, and European institutions linked to the project's topics. Furthermore, partners

will take a proactive role in participating in different initiatives driven by these projects or European associations, contributing project content to enrich the material featured in institutions' newsletters, public websites, and publications if possible.

SuPreAM consortium has to organise or participate in at least 3 joint clustering dissemination activities until the project's completion. Up to M6, SuPreAM clustering actions include the collaborative participation of the project in the SteelTech Congress (October 2023, Bilbao) together with the RFCS projects HELIX, COOPHS, NewAIMS, Sup3rForm and HELIX.

11.3.1 Potential clustering with European initiatives, associations and platforms

Clustering actions, synergies and cooperation will be established with significant initiatives and platforms, some of which are listed in Table 9.

Table 9: First list of proposed identified associations, institutions, initiatives and clusters.

Name	Description	Website
AM PLATFORM – European Technology Platform in Additive Manufacturing	The AM-platform is the largest and oldest community of stakeholders for all subject related to Additive Manufacturing (hereafter named AM) in Europe. Currently, more than 700 members from more than 25 countries are part of this network. The AM-platform is active since 2007 (formerly as the RM-platform). The objective of the AM-platform is to contribute to a coherent strategy, understanding, development, dissemination and exploitation of AM. A point of networking, reference and coordination.	https://www.rm-platform.com/
Metallurgy Europe Cluster	The Metallurgy EU cluster established the Metallurgy Europe Research' Programme that can design, develop and deploy the next set of revolutionary alloys and composites for key industrial applications, including energy, renewables, mobility and health. This programme initiative is timely, practically useful and economically necessary.	https://metallurgy-europe.eu/
MAV – Advanced Materials Cluster of Catalonia	The Clúster MAV is the leading cluster in advanced materials and their technologies. We are a non-profit, proactive and open association whose purpose is to make businesses and organisations in the advanced materials sector value chain more competitive, thus helping to consolidate the industry as a whole.	https://www.cluster-mav.com/?lang=en
EPoSS – the European Association on Smart Systems Integration	EPoSS is the European Association leading the development and integration of intelligent and green Smart Systems technologies and solutions for a sustainable society. The European Technology Platform on Smart Systems Integration is an industry-driven policy initiative, defining R&D and innovation needs as well as policy requirements related to Smart Systems Integration and integrated Micro- and Nanosystems.	https://www.smart-systems-integration.org/
EUMAT - The European Technology Platform for Advanced Engineering Materials and Technologies	EuMaT has the aim to contribute to the best relation and dialogue between industry, R&D actors and institutions aiming at improving the coordination and synergies at national and European level in the field of materials R&D.	https://www.eumat.eu/en

WorldSteel Association	The WorldSteel Association is one of the largest and most dynamic industry associations in the world, with members in every major steel-producing country. Worldsteel represents steel producers, national and regional steel industry associations, and steel research institutes. Members represent around 85% of global steel production.	https://worldsteel.org/
EMMC- The European Materials Modelling Council	The non-profit Association, EMMC ASBL, was created in 2019 to ensure continuity, growth and sustainability of EMMC activities for all stakeholders including modellers, materials data scientists, software owners, translators and manufacturers in Europe. The EMMC considers the integration of materials modelling and digitalisation critical for more agile and sustainable product development.	https://emmc.eu
EMCC- European Materials Characterisation Council	The EMCC is devoted to establish a community of European stakeholders in the process of developing and improving characterisation tools in order to bring the development of nanomaterials and advanced materials in Europe into end products more successfully.	http://characterisation.eu
ESTEP - European Steel Technology Platform	The European Steel Technology Platform (ESTEP) brings together all the major stakeholders in the European steel industry. ESTEP's mission aims to engage in collaborative EU actions and projects on technology, which are tackling EU challenges (notably on renewable energy, climate change (low-carbon emission), circular economy) in order to create a sustainable EU steel industry.	https://www.estep.eu
PLATEA – Spanish Steel Technological Platform	The Spanish Steel Technology Platform, PLATEA, was born led by the industry, presenting itself as an environment of intense work, collaboration and commitment to achieving new advances and initiatives in R&D&I that result in benefits for the steel sector.	https://aceroplatea.es/
CHS - Centre for High Performance Steel	CHS creates prerequisites for sustainable development and use of the high-performance steel of the future through research and education linked to our interdisciplinary competence profile.	https://www.ltu.se/c/entres/chs?l=en
Jernkontoret	Jernkontoret, the Swedish iron and steel producers' association, safeguards the industry's interests through working for the best possible preconditions for operations in Sweden.	https://www.jernkontoret.se/en/
ManuKET - Spanish Advanced Manufacturing Technology Platform	The primary aim of the MANU-KET platform is to provide a global and inclusive vision of advanced manufacturing and industrial production technologies that enable planning, promoting and boosting research, technological development and innovation activities (R&D&i) that contribute to a more competitive industry and provide solutions for challenges that society will face in the future.	https://www.manufacturing-ket.com/manu-ket/
MANUFUTURE – European Technology Platform on Advanced Manufacturing	The mission of the European Technology Platform MANUFUTURE is to propose, develop and implement a strategy based on Research and Innovation, capable of speeding up the rate of industrial transformation to high-added-value products, processes and services, securing high-skills employment and winning a major share of world Manufacturing output in the knowledge-driven economy.	https://www.manufuture.org/
POOL.NET - Portuguese Tooling Network Association	Pool-Net: Portuguese Tooling & Plastics Network is the association responsible for dynamizing the Portuguese Cluster of Competitiveness Engineering & Tooling, namely through the	https://app.toolingportugal.com/en/

	implementation of the strategy of collective efficiency defined for this sector.	
Andalucía Aerospace Cluster	Andalucía Aerospace is the Andalusian aerospace business cluster whose task is to promote the interests of the Andalusian aerospace sector and stimulate growth at the national and international level.	https://andaluciaaerospaace.com/
EPPN – European Pilot Production Network	The EU-funded EPPN project aims to enhance European competitiveness by utilising existing pilot line production facilities in nanotechnology and advanced material technologies.	https://www.eppnetwork.com
ELCA- European Lightweight Alliance	The overall objective of the European Lighting Cluster Alliance, ELCA, is to gather forces on a European level in order to increase the competitiveness of the European lighting industries.	http://elcacluster.eu
ACEA – the European Automobile Manufacturers Association	The European Automobile Manufacturers' Association (ACEA) represents the 15 major Europe-based car, van, truck and bus makers.	https://www.acea.be
ERMA – European Raw Materials Alliance	The European Raw Materials Alliance (ERMA) aims to make Europe economically more resilient by diversifying its supply chains, creating jobs, attracting investments to the raw materials value chain, fostering innovation, training young talents and contributing to the best enabling framework for raw materials and the Circular Economy worldwide.	https://erma.eu
EMIRI - The Energy Materials Industrial Research Initiative.	EMIRI is driving forward research and innovation in the advanced materials for low-carbon energy applications. Innovative energy technologies are required to cost-effectively meet Europe's energy and climate change challenges.	https://emiri.eu
CLEPA – European Association of Automotive Suppliers	CLEPA is the voice of European automotive suppliers, representing over 3.000 companies which employ 5.000.000 employees.	https://clepa.eu
EUROFER - European Steel Association	The European Steel Association (EUROFER) AISBL represents the entirety of steel production in the European Union. The European Steel Association's members are steel companies and national steel federations throughout the EU. The major steel companies and national steel federations in Switzerland and Turkey are associate members.	https://www.eurofer.eu

11.3.2 Potential clustering with related projects

Cooperating and partnering with other projects and initiatives enhances the collective voice when engaging with target audiences. Table 10 enumerates various linked projects and/or initiatives affiliated with SuPreAM.

Table 10: Initial list of SuPreAM sister projects.

Initiative	Short description
FLEXCRASH (ending August 2026)	The Flexcrash project, coordinated by Eurecat, is developing a flexible and hybrid manufacturing technology using aluminium alloys and based on applying surface patterns by additive manufacturing onto preformed parts.

Sup3rForm (ending December 2026)	Sup3rForm is a RFCS project coordinated by Eurecat with the objective to exploit the full potential of 3rd Generation Q&P and medium-Mn steels with superior formability for lightweight structural applications in future mobility, addressing the need for lighter, more efficient, safer and economic vehicles by boosting the implementation of new high-performance steel solutions, such as 3rd Generation AHSS, with higher strength and crashworthiness.
COOPHS (ending December 2026)	Funded under the RFCS programme and coordinated by Eurecat, COOPHS project works to improve the production of low CO2 steel for the automotive sector, through the development of more sustainable processing methodologies that will contribute to its decarbonization.
NewAIMS (ending March 2027)	The NewAIMS project aims to research, study and demonstrate strategies to obtain cost-effective high-performance steel in AM processes, through concepts of modified AM with integrated heat treatments. The project is funded by the RFCS European programme and coordinated by Eurecat.
ALABAMA (ending December 2028)	The ALABAMA project aims to develop and mature adaptive laser technologies for AM. The objective is to lower decrease the porosity and to tailor the microstructure of the deposited material by shaping the laser beam, both temporally and spatially, during the AM process. Eurecat participates in ALABAMA's project verifying that the built material fulfills the requirements by conducting advanced characterization on coupons and on use-cases.

11.4 Scientific publications

The SuPreAM project will disseminate its main research, findings and results through the periodic publication of reports or outcomes in specific scientific journals relevant to the project's fields. A **minimum of four publications in peer-reviewed journals** throughout the project's duration is planned. An **additional objective is to collaborate on at least two papers involving the participation of more than two partners**.

Due to the unpredictable nature of results appearances and technical maturity, the timing of these publications is subject to discussion and adjustment. In the periodical WP progress meetings, pivotal outcomes will be discussed, enabling partners to determine timelines and identify appropriate conference proceedings or relevant journals for publication. The selected journals will be customized to match the specific characteristics of the results, spanning areas such as steel research, additive manufacturing, and materials science, among others.

SuPreAM partners will guarantee open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to most of the peer-reviewed scientific publications through gold open access, whenever available (provided via the published when an article is published), and/or green open access via an online repository (Open Aire / Zenodo) to ensure the long-term preservation and availability of the publications.

Additionally, publications will be published and disseminated through researchers' individual ResearchGate pages whenever applicable, expanding the visibility of the project's research outputs across the academic and scientific community and beyond.

On the other hand, partners will also consider the submission of papers and articles to the Open Research Europe, an innovative open access publishing platform offering rapid publication and open peer reviewed.

In this sense, as soon as the first scientific article will be published, a SuPreAM Zenodo community will be created to allocate all the project-related research publications.

An initial list of open access journals of interest for publishing SuPreAM results has been defined, as follows:

Table 11: Identified scientific journals of interest for publication.

Name of the journal	Link
Advances in Industrial and Manufacturing Engineering	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/advances-in-industrial-and-manufacturing-engineering
Steel Research International	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1869344
Materials Science and Engineering: A	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/materials-science-and-engineering-a
Journal of Materials Processing Technology	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-materials-processing-technology
Metallurgical and Materials Transactions A	https://link.springer.com/journal/11661
Advanced Engineering Materials	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/15272648
Metals	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/metals
Materials	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/materials
International Journal of Mechanical Sciences	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-mechanical-sciences
ISIJ International	https://isijint.net
Journal of Materials Science & Technology	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/journal-of-materials-science-and-technology
Engineering Fracture Mechanics	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/engineering-fracture-mechanics
Steel Research International	https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/journal/1869344

11.4.1 Scientific production calendar

From December 2023 (M6) onward, partners have identified the following topics as potential subjects for upcoming publications, signifying a proactive initiative in shaping the project's scientific contributions.

Table 12: Proposal of scientific publications topics planned.

Topic of the publication	Partners involved	Planning
Surface integrity characterization	EUT, IDO, DRT, GSC	M24
EDM modelling	CIMNE, DRT	M30
Surface model development	CIMNE, LTU, IDO, EUT	M36
Finishing operations	EUT, DRT	M40

12. Planning

The execution of the dissemination and communication plan will align with the scheduled calendar of actions as illustrated below.

ACTIVITIES	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
	Jan-24	Feb-24	Mar-24	Apr-24	May-24	Jun-24	Jul-24	Aug-24	Sep-24	Oct-24	Nov-24	Dec-24
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media update		X		X		X		X		X		X
Participation to dissemination events					X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
	M19	M20	M21	M22	M23	M24	M25	M26	M27	M28	M29	M30
	Jan-25	Feb-25	Mar-25	Apr-25	May-25	Jun-25	Jul-25	Aug-25	Sep-25	Oct-25	Nov-25	Dec-25
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media update		X		X		X		X		X	X	X
Participation to dissemination events	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
First project webinar			X									
	M31	M32	M33	M34	M35	M36	M37	M38	M39	M40	M41	M42
	Jan-26	Feb-26	Mar-26	Apr-26	May-26	Jun-26	Jul-26	Aug-26	Sep-26	Oct-26	Nov-26	Dec-26
Website update	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Social media update		X		X		X		X		X		X
Participation to dissemination events	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X

This project has received funding from the European Union's Research Fund for Coal and Steel (RFCS): project num. 101112346. This document reflects only SuPreAM consortium view and neither the European Commission or any associated parties are responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Second project webinar						X						
Update project flyer										X		
Project final video												X
Final project's press release												X
Final webinar												X

13. Conclusions

This document outlines plans in the realms of communication and dissemination, highlighting the key achievements and advancements made in the first six months of the SuPreAM project. It provides a comprehensive dissemination strategy, detailing the materials and strategies employed and planned for external dissemination. While a series of communication and dissemination actions have been outlined, the document acknowledges the likelihood of additional dissemination opportunities emerging as the project unfolds.

The consortium views this plan as an initial strategy, subject to regular updates and reviews. Future steps involve engaging all partners in identifying further dissemination opportunities and collectively agreeing on key avenues. Collaboration among partners will be actively encouraged through regular dissemination calls, during which the existing plan will be scrutinized, and future actions will be deliberated upon.

The progress made in the ensuing months and years will be documented in review reports and also in internal consortium meetings.